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Title: Intimate partner violence and shared custody: concerns and contradictions from the findings of a sociological research study

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Introduction

This paper stems from a multi-site research study in Europe – STRESS-Mums project – that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 843976 (Tartari 2019).

The research study focuses on the *transition* from double parenthood to lone parenthood, and, in particular, during that transition, on the situation of judicial evaluation for child custody and courts’

decisions for allowances and other obligations. Using the approach of Institutional Ethnography (IE), this project collects data in Belgium, Italy, Spain, and the UK.

The general aim of this project is the investigation of the *disjunctures* between single mothers' everyday experiences and the framework defined by the law during the process of transition due to the separation. It aims to understand how the legal and judicial system works with mothers during the process of separation and divorce when they have custody of their children or when children live predominantly with the mother. The sample includes mothers who had an experience of intimate partner violence. With the term “single mothers” in this project, we refer to mothers who are separated or divorced.

This paper utilizes data from the Italian fieldwork and focuses on the emerging need for differentiating high conflict and family violence (like intimate partner violence) and the need of understanding how shared custody works or does not work.

The paper analyzes the experiences of mothers who were victims of intimate partner violence and the decisions of courts about child custody, the practices of other institutions involved in protecting mothers and children, and the relationships with the fathers.

In the Italian sample, a consistent part of them had experience of IPV and we will see the disjunctures between their experiences and needs and the framework defined by the law and by the legal procedures.

The aim of this project is also to contribute to improving the current law, the legal procedures and policies concerning children custody, parents' evaluation, and mothers' needs.

A review of research studies already conducted in Europe and Western countries highlights many problems for single mothers after separation or divorce, like poverty, work problems, health problems, and a lack of support by welfare systems, systems that are different among EU countries (see, for instance, Bernardi & Mortelmans 2018; Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado 2018; Mortelmans 2020).

None of these studies seemed to have sociologically considered the crucial transition of the judicial evaluation for children's custody. This is an important transition in shaping the trajectories of these mothers and their children. And none of these studies considered the everyday strategies and practices that these mothers use to claim and achieve social inclusion and legitimization during that transition.

In the framework of the Institutional ethnography, the sociological approach that I use in this project, institutional discourses and practices come from different kinds of texts which are the actual law about shared custody, the civil and criminal codes for lawyers and judges, the codes of civil and criminal procedures but also other kinds of texts like guidelines for psychologists and social workers who evaluate those mothers.

IE defines the research question as research problematic, the problematic from which we can start our investigation. The literature suggested the need to investigate the *disjunctures* between the mothers' everyday experience and the framework defined by the law, codes, and guidelines.

Methods

Using the approach of Institutional Ethnography (IE), this project collects data in Belgium, Italy, Spain, and the UK.

IE (Smith 1990; Smith 2005) is an empirical investigation that allows understanding the links among the local settings of everyday life (at a micro-sociological level, the informants' standpoint), the organizations, and trans-local processes of administration and governance (the meso and macro levels). The term 'institution' does not refer to a type of organization, but clusters of text-mediated relations organized around particular ruling functions (e.g., education or health care). In other words, from the informants' standpoint, IE investigates organizational processes that are coordinated by texts.

The choice of IE in this project is due to its ability to explicate the tensions produced by the social organization of knowledge during this specific transition from double to single parenthood. IE investigates a defined section of the social world from the standpoint of the organization of the 'work' of individuals. IE aims to discover 'how things work'.

In the frame of IE approach, I used different tools: in-depth interviews with mothers, judicial professionals and experts of gender issues, documents-based interviews, analysis of legal documents (like petitions and decisions from the courts or reports of the social services to the courts), and photo-voice sessions involving mothers and professionals.

Through an 'intersectional' approach, I recruited mothers who had a legal petition lodged with the court for sole children custody (petition that was accepted or rejected by the court).

Mothers' point of view

In this section, I will present the early results from the Italian fieldwork selecting the cases of IPV among the mothers that I interviewed. Firstly, I will show the analysis of the interviews with the mothers and then the data from the interviews with the professionals

Mothers in this sample had experiences of IPV from a mild to a severe degree, a different number of children, children with disabilities, a different length of their marriage or relationship, different ages, different social, economic, and cultural conditions.

Usually, they requested the legal separation after repeated episodes of IPV, usually after the most violent one that is, often, after that IPV happened in front of or involving children.

Their accounts present delays in asking for separation due to financial issues (for example, mothers without a job) and family issues (for example, mothers with any kind of family support networks)

There is sometimes violence against children or witnessed violence of children who were present to episodes of IPV of the father against the mother

For all these mothers, with a few exceptions, there was a protection order. However, they highlight problems in making the order effective and the problem in managing contacts and communication with the fathers when they have shared custody of children. Often they had no help from a parental coordinator or other professionals and they should manage contacts by themselves.

Always their accounts underline issues with feelings of loneliness and that they were not believed by the court or police about their IPV experience.

They highlight also the problem of the length of the lawsuits because different courts manage the files in civil and crime sectors and sometimes courts have no specific training about IPV.

They perceive the importance of having a voice in that process of transition but often they underline that the voice is silenced or neglected. Their capacity of “having a voice” is not linked to social, economic, or individual characteristics, but mostly to personal characteristics.

Regarding the topic of children's custody when mothers have experienced IPV, the cases presented very different evaluations. They are the following ones:

Court's decisions about children custody include both joint custody and sole custody

- Sometimes, lawyers suggested to the mothers to not ask for sole custody also in severe cases of IPV, witnessed violence or abuse against children.
- On the other hand, mothers had experiences of many problematic conditions in a shared custody regime, in particular when IPV had a severe degree. They have to manage not only negative emotions and feelings but also practical, social, and bureaucratic aspects of everyday life without communication and sometimes they have any kind of help from institutions in managing these aspects. Their need is that institutions (courts) should have more consideration about practical aspects of their and their children's everyday life
- Sometimes these mothers had an experience of children's custody assigned to social services because the court adopted this decision as a solution to “balance” the rights in a situation perceived as a high conflictual one. The mothers perceived this decision as unfair, like a delegitimation of their parental role and a punishment.

- Court-appointed investigations on parental responsibilities (by experts in the field of psychology) often are perceived not useful to solve or clarify the situation (suggestions are disregarded or not applied by the fathers) or the investigation is conducted not enough in-depth.

Furthermore, investigation on financial aspects is perceived as not sufficient and done in-depth to ensure equality and equity for alimony and children maintenance during the process of evaluation.

Professionals' point of view

The interviews with lawyers highlight both problems and solutions to the disjunctures that the mothers underlined in their experience.

The first feedback from professionals' experience focuses on mothers and IPV. They underline that protection orders present some limits in their effectiveness and they need improvement, without contradictions, they need to find coherence between the legal abstract instrument and its actual application in daily life.

Furthermore, they underline the existence of a problem concerning the consideration for mothers' specific vulnerabilities, like legal, financial, emotional ones, that affect delays in asking for help and protection or separation. The needs concern improving legal support and welfare (with ad hoc policy), need of training for professionals, need of a cultural/systemic change

Then, here I discuss the feedback from the professionals on the process for the custody evaluation.

They highlight the following specific problems:

The first one concerns the need for differentiation between high-conflict families and IPV. This need concerns the law framework, the legal procedures, and the procedures of other professionals involved in the process of evaluation. They underline the need for change because shared custody as a legal framework does not often work in these situations.

Therefore, they underline the need for tailor-made decisions, the need for specific training for professionals, the need for specific courts with a specific formation and training.

Then, the experience of professionals looks at the “custody of children to social services” as a problematic condition in managing practical aspects without proper human resources from the social services that are often overwhelmed by requests. So these professionals highlight the need to assess more carefully the practical consequences of this kind of custody on the everyday life of children and mothers.

Then, professionals explain that often judges ask too many and rely too much on court-appointed experts’ evaluations. They explain that these experts’ evaluations are not useful in solving conflicts or in analyzing well the situation: these professionals highlight the need for specific training on IPV and gender aspects for these professionals.

Another problem that these professionals underline concerns the prejudices shown against mothers who are IPV victims (for example, when these mothers show their concerns about children's contacts when they are not believed about their accusations). Professionals highlight the need for cultural change and the improvement of in-depth evaluations that could consider gender-sensitive aspects.

Furthermore, the experience of professionals about the process for custody evaluation highlights the frequent difficulties of communication between parents and highlights the need for different instruments/tools, like supervised contacts, supervised visitations, specialized monitoring, etc.

These aspects require more investments in supervision, in professionals who supervise parents and children.

Finally, professionals underline the need for the creation of highly specialized courts on family issues and IPV, the need for improvement of coordination between courts, social services, and other institutions involved (here again the problem on human resources in these organizations is stressed).

Then, these professionals underline the need of avoiding secondary victimization of IPV victims into the courts.

Furthermore, they stress the fact that custody evaluation is a collaborative process between parents, institutions, and professionals with a strong accent on personal, professional, and institutional responsibilities, where personal and professional “interests” should not overcome ethical aspects. They ask for improvement of training, and a systemic change for the evaluation of responsibilities and ethics issues.

Conclusions

To conclude, these are raw data and I have not yet drawn on them with a more theoretical analysis like IE would require (Smith 2005). However, some important data and aspects emerge from this fieldwork.

I would like to add a significant piece of information that confirms the results here discussed. A network of experts a few months ago in Italy highlighted the need for a “gender-sensitive” and a “gender-responsive” training to evaluate parental responsibilities and to get involved as a professional in these civil lawsuits (see the document published by the Italian network D.i.Re, July 2020). Like other professionals underline, the need is to find a good balance between children's rights to be safe (physically, emotionally) and a shared custody framework. The highlighted need is that a rigid law framework should not prevail on children’s real, material rights of physical and mental wellbeing. Furthermore, how to reach this well-being should be evaluated carefully.

Data from the interviews with professionals and mothers stress that shared custody does not always work as a legal prescription and shared parenting does not always work as a good practice in situations with IPV. Therefore, there is evidence for the need for tailor-made decisions.

At a more general theoretical level, a reflection is needed to understand if the gender equality framework can mask inequalities and if, with equity, we – we as professionals – can recognize and legitimize the “labour” - the “hidden work”, the “efforts” - that IPV survivors do (for the

interactionist notions of “work” and “labour” see Strauss et al. 1975; Hochschild 1979; Griffith, Smith 2005; Smith 2006).

In my research and other studies, a key factor to be stressed is the investigation of the link between orthodox representations of parenting and parenthood and professionals’ decisions.

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